

PREPARATION OF Ni-TiC METAL COMPOSITE MATERIAL IN SPACE

Sennosuke Takahashi

National Research Institute for Metals
Nakameguro, Meguro-ku, Tokyo 153
Japan

Summary

Ni matrix composite materials strengthened by TiC whisker or particle were studied on the effect of low gravity at their processing. The sintered samples of Ni-10%Mo-30%TiC whisker and Ni-10%Mo-20%TiC particle were melted, pressed at about 2MPa and rapidly cooled during 6 minutes under low gravity by use of ballistic flight of rocket, and recovered. From the analytical results of flight samples by optical and electron microscopy, EPMA and AES, ununiformity of TiC distribution caused by convection and segregation induced by gravity were not recognized.

Introduction

Generally speaking, it is not easy to prepare the composite metals or alloys with ceramics. One of the successful examples of those type is Ni-ThO₂ alloy where ThO₂ is dispersed as particles under 2 vol%, however better performance has not been reported by adding more than about 2 vol% of ThO₂. Usually the wettability between oxide and metal is not good, therefore it is difficult to disperse oxide particles in metal matrix. The addition of much oxide promote coagulation of oxide each other and reduce strengthening effect by dispersion of particles. This effect is caused by inhibiting dislocation movement in matrix metal, and all we need is the volume of dispersion particles to do it. Accordingly the fundamental physical properties of this composite material, that is, metallic properties do not much change.

Oxide Dispersion Strengthening Super Alloy (ODS) which is progressively developed recently is not so different from dispersion strengthening alloy except using super heat resistant alloy as matrix metal and mechanical alloying process. There is another strengthening method by adding plenty volume of ceramics whereas dispersion strengthened alloy is added relatively small amount of ceramics. It is a composite material of ceramic powder as a main component and metal or alloy as binding material, therefore it shows characteristic as ceramic itself and this fact makes its application to engine materials difficult. Author planed to develop the better heat resistant alloy including relatively large volume such as 20% of ceramics.

This work is similar to those mentioned above on the point of using ceramics, but different on the following point, that is, main component is nickel alloy and 30% TiC whisker or 20% paticle (wt %) is used as strengthening material. TiC whisker or particle of 4.9 g/cm³ in density and Nickel alloy of about twice as density as TiC have to be well processed into composite material. A proper method to be thought is uniform blending TiC with metal powder, sintering and melting. The melting at the last stage makes connection of metal particle each other or metal and TiC firm, and the composite material obtained by this process shows high strength as a construction material. However this process is not successful under gravity, because of the difference of density. Moreover high melting point materials like this bring about temperature gradient at their melting and it makes convection. Therefore the sintered materials which were carefully prepared by dispersing TiC uniformly change to segregation structure by melting. The segregation is difficult to avoid under the ground where the gravity works, while convection by temperature difference and floating or sedimentation by density difference do not occur under non-gravity environment. Then the processing experiment of Ni-TiC composite material was planed by mounting the small electric furnace and its controll system on the sounding rocket.

Preparation of samples

Ni-Mo-TiC whisker sample. Many kinds of whiskers can be thought as a high strength material, but those whiskers are tangled. TiC whiskers become easily individuals by loosing them in solution and this is one of the most important reasons why whisker was chosen out of the other kinds of whiskers. TiC whisker was offered by Government Industrial Research Institute of Japan, Osaka, and had 10 - 50 μ m in thickness, 500 - 2000 μ m in length. TiC reacts on Ni-Mo matrix at near 1350°C according to the differential thermal analysis as shown in Figure 1 (1). They were plated by rhodium to disturb above reaction. The followings are why Ni-Mo alloy was chosen as a matrix ; 1) good wettability on TiC whisker, 2) good heat resistancy, 3)relatively easy to handle, 4) easy to get. The problem is how to disperse whiskers in Ni-Mo matrix. The directionally oriented TiC whisker was prepared in this flight experiment as follows; the Ni-Mo-TiC whisker mixture was extruded through small circular holes to

Figure 1 Differential thermal curves of the Ni-20wt%TiC-Mo system containing 0, 5 and 15 wt%Mo (1).

On the sample obtained by flight experiment. Figure 3 shows the microstructure of the cross section of Ni-Mo-TiC whisker sample. It can be seen that the TiC whisker of hexagonal cross section aligns vertical to the photograph plane. The annual ring like structure which shows the growing process of whisker crystal by chemical vapour deposition can be also seen in it. The EPMA (X-ray microanalysis) by line scanning for Ni-Mo-TiC whisker is shown in Figure 4. It is found that the Mo elements highly concentrate on the boundary of Ni matrix and TiC whiskers (2). However the movement of Mo into TiC particle was rarely recognized in the sintered Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample. The results of more precision analysis by AES on above samples coincide with those of EPMA on Mo distribution.

Figure 5 shows the outlook of Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample recovered from the flight experiment. It is observed that the sample was completely melted and

align TiC whiskers unidirectionally. The mixture was made by the aqueous solution of ammonium alginate to extrude easily. The extruded sticklike sample was dried, then heated at 1100°C for 30 minutes in order to evaporate alginate. The sample for the flight experiment prepared as described above had a composition of Ni-10wt%-30wt%TiC and its weight was 3.85 g.

Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample. The samples were prepared by blending Ni, Mo and TiC particles of 1-2 μm in size by a high speed mixer having rotary wings of 8000 rpm, pressing the blended powder into cylindrical form under a pressure of about 200 MPa, and then heating at about 1260°C in vacuum. The composition of this sample was Ni-10% Mo-20%TiC. In the preparation of flight experiment samples, the attention was paid to remove gases from sample and sample-ampoule, because when they become bubbles by heating under low gravity condition, it is difficult either to push them out by pressing or to come out by floating like on the ground. Therefore the samples were kept at 1260°C for a long time, and then hot-pressed to dense, and cooled in vacuum. The weight, length and composition of sample are as follows; weight: 21.98 g, length: 36.9 mm, diameter: 9.9 mm, composition: Ni-10%Mo-20%TiC particle.

Experiment and results

Figure 2 shows the temperature-time curve of the electric furnace used for the flight experiment of Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample. From Fig.2, it is found that sample was melted within about 2 minutes after heating, kept at near 1450°C for about 2 minutes, then cooled. The temperature of sample reached near 700°C in 500 seconds after launch as expected.

then solidified . Figure 6 shows the carbon piston to press molten sample (left side), sample (center), sample container made of carbon -sample ampoule -(right side).

Figure 7 shows the optical microstructure of the cross section obtained by slicing and polishing the cylindrical sample. It seems to be a good structure of uniformly dispersed TiC particles in Ni-Mo matrix.

Figure 8 shows the microstructure of the cross section of ground sample prepared under the same condition as flight experiment.

Figure 2 Temperature - time curve of the electric furnace used for the flight experiment of Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample.

Figure 3 Microstructure of the cross section of Ni-Mo-TiC whisker sample obtained by flight experiment.

Figure 4 Line scanning curves for Ni and Mo elements in the Ni-Mo-TiC whisker sample by EPMA.

Figure 5 Outlook of Ni-Mo-TiC particle sample recovered from the flight experiment.

Figure 6 Carbon piston rod to press molten sample(left side), sample(center), and sample container made of carbon(right side)

Figure 7 Microstructure of flight experiment sample.

Figure 8 Microstructure of ground experiment sample.

Considerations

The behavior of TiC particle or whisker in molten Ni is dominated by the gravity level, surface energy between TiC and molten nickel, and random walk of TiC.

Floating of TiC. The floating distance of TiC in molten nickel during 100 seconds is calculated from Stokes' law at various gravity levels as shown Figure 9. The distance becomes longer as the increase of particle size and

Figure 9 Floating distance of TiC in molten nickel during 100 Seconds.

the migration distance of particle of 1 - 2 μm is negligibly small under the level of 10⁻³ - 10⁻⁴ G. In this case the time condition of 100 seconds is introduced because the sample is kept in the molten state for about 100 seconds during the flight experiment. The calculated values from the equation (1) are plotted in the double logarithmic scale as shown in Fig. 9.

$$I_s = \frac{d^2}{18\eta} (\rho - \rho_0) G t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

- where I_s ; moving distance of particle
- d ; diameter assuming the particle to be a small globe
- η ; viscosity of molten material

- ρ ; density of particle
- ρ_0 ; density of molten matrix
- G ; acceleration of gravity
- t ; time.

The values of 7.68 g/cm³ for ρ_0 , the measured density at 1550°C and 6.9 cp for η , the viscosity of the molten nickel, and 4.92 g/cm³ for ρ , the density of the TiC were used in the above calculation (3,4).

Effect of wettability between TiC and Ni. The good wettability between TiC and Ni is preferable to disperse TiC in the molten nickel alloy and to remove voids from sintered and hot pressed materials. It was reported that the contact angle became zero by adding 10% molybdenum to nickel(5), therefore molybdenum was used as a component of nickel alloy to improve the wettability to TiC in this experiment. Let us consider the wettability in more detail. The relation between force f which push cylindrical bundle of whisker into molten alloy in vertical to the surface and the contact angle θ is obtained from the equation (2),

$$f = - \frac{4v \gamma \cos \theta}{d} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

- where v ; volume percent of cylindrical whisker
- d ; diameter of cylindrical whisker
- γ ; surface tension of molten alloy
- θ ; contact angle of molten alloy to cylindrical whisker.

The equation (2) was introduced assuming that the cross section of the cylindrical whisker bundle was close packed. From this equation it is found that the push force f can take either positive or negative sign. Since the contact angle θ of molten nickel alloy to TiC is zero as mentioned above, the equation (2) becomes as follows,

$$f = - \frac{4v \gamma}{d} \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

If the parameters of volume percent of TiC, v , and the surface tension of molten alloy γ , is constant, the force f increases inversely as the size of TiC. The smaller the diameter of TiC becomes, the stronger the force is. It means fine particle of TiC is easy to disperse in molten alloy. From above consideration, it seem that the force is necessary not to push TiC, but to remove voids which remain in the molten sample because of the sintering or hot pressing process. These voids can not float and come out of molten sample under the weightless conditions.

Random walk. The movement by random walk must be considered when the particle size becomes small. Assuming that the particle of diameter d randomly walks in molten metal by distance I_r for time t at the temperature T , I_r can be obtained from the following equation;

$$I_r = \left(\frac{2kTt}{3\pi\eta d} \right)^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where k is Boltzmann's constant. If we use the data of 6.9 cp for the viscosity at 1550°C of molten nickel, we can obtain random walk I_r . Figure 10 shows the double logarithmic plot of I_r to the particle size.

Figure 10 Random walk of TiC particle in molten nickel during 100 seconds.

A 1 μm size particle migrates 8.8 μm and a 2 μm size particle migrates 6.2 μm during 100 seconds. A long migration distance does not always mean a segregation of particles because the migration of particle is random. However a long migration distance causes a higher tendency for particle coagulation since the particles in the range of such distance have a greater frequency of collision. In this case, collision may not always occur combination of particles. There may be molten metal atom between collision particles and the wettability of molten nickel alloy to TiC is also considered to be an unnegligible factor for coagulation. Accordingly the effect of random walk can be regarded as not so large in the relation of TiC and molten nickel alloy even if TiC particle is fine.

Conclusion

Two kinds of samples, Ni-Mo-TiC whisker and Ni-Mo-TiC particle were successfully recovered from ballistic flight of rocket. From this flight experiment, relations of G level at 3 axes of X,Y,Z vs time and temperature of furnace vs time were obtained. From the structural analysis by optical and electron microscope, EPMA and AES for these recovered samples, ununiformity of TiC distribution caused by convection and segregation induced by gravity were not recognized. The analysis of element distribution such as Ni, Mo, Ti and C showed the distinguished difference between the flight melted and the ground melted samples. The effect of the Marangoni current on the flight samples could not be cleared.

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